

PROCESS INDUCED DISTORTION IN TEXTILE COMPOSITES: Consolidation Pressure Effects

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ABSTRACT

Fabric geometry distortion (i.e., waviness and tow misalignment) is often cited as a possible cause of data scatter and lower compressive stiffness and strength in textile composites. Strength differences of as much as 40% have been seen in composites with essentially the same basic material and structural properties – e.g., tow angles, tow size, interlacing geometry. Yet, the current understanding of this effect is primarily anecdotal. Based on a controlled study of the effect of consolidation pressure, this paper shows that high pressures occurring when direct tow-tow contact is achieved results in distortion and subsequent strength loss.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most critical problems facing the composites industry today is cost. With the emphasis being placed more and more on commercial applications, composites must prove their ability to compete on an economic basis in addition to satisfying engineering requirements. Textile composites provide one viable option for lower cost composites. The time and cost of labor intensive hand layup processes is not acceptable for medium to high volume markets such as the automotive industry. However, because of the existing technology for rapid, automated manufacturing of textile structures, the use of textile preforms and thermoforming or liquid molding (e.g., RTM) processes can significantly reduce the time and complexity of fiber placement. In addition to decreasing the production time, textile preforms represent a complex interlacing of fibers that minimizes large, continuous interfaces, making the material less susceptible to catastrophic delamination, crack propagation, and impact damage.

Unfortunately, even with the highly automated textile processes, some degree of geometric variability is unavoidable. As more and more experiments have been run on various types of textile composites, recurring phrases of “data scatter” and “unexpected strength variations” appear in the literature. Departures from the expected mean are typically attributed to some distortion of the fiber geometry – e.g., tow misalignment, fiber waviness, wrinkling [1, 2]. Yet, very little quantitative evidence exists on what causes these distortions and when their effects become important. There is currently no clear understanding of all the mechanisms involved in causing the large deviations in strength that occur during testing of actual materials. The focus of this paper is on the role of forming and consolidation pressure on distortion and, subsequently, strength.

MODELING OF STRENGTH AND STIFFNESS

Large deviations in strength are not acceptable for structural components – i.e., design allowables must be established within reasonable bounds. Herein lies the importance of accurate models for composite behavior. There are several existing models for predicting composite stiffness of textile composites. These models range from classical lamination theory (CLT) based approaches (e.g., mosaic model, undulation model, bridging model, fabric geometry model [3]) to finite element models [4] and analytical models [5] based on idealized yarn geometries. All of these models have succeeded at predicting stiffness within a reasonable degree of accuracy (e.g., within 10%). Unfortunately, the same cannot be said of strength predictions. Some models have succeeded in reaching predictions reasonably close to the mean experimental values, but none have really addressed the mechanisms causing the observed variations in experimental data.

Pastore [6] discussed some of the process variations affecting fiber geometry in plain weave and braided fabrics, showing measurements of a $\pm 10^\circ$ range in the in-plane and out-of-plane angles of warp and weft yarns in a plain weave. From these measurements, he was able to predict the expected stiffness variations as a function of the standard deviations of the angles. Analysis of strength variations in this paper and others, however, has been limited to a qualitative discussion of stochastic modeling. Stiffness models generally attain better results because stiffness is primarily a function of the averaged response of the material. In contrast, strength can be dominated by the “weakest link”, lending itself more naturally to incorporation of stochastic modeling. In order to develop a robust stochastic model for strength, a better understanding is needed of the mechanisms governing the failure. In testing done by Cox [2], kink bands are cited as a major cause of failure. Therefore, the process factors leading to distortion such as premature yarn buckling are of primary interest.

GENERAL OBSERVATIONS

Since all composites manufacturing involves some consolidation step, it seemed reasonable to first examine the effect of applied pressure. A broad qualitative survey of various textile structures – stitched, biaxial and triaxial 2D braids, plain weaves, and weaves made with powder towpregs – produced few surprises. With larger compaction ratios typical of powder towpreg materials, the amount and degree of distortion increased, and more distortion was observed in structures with more z-direction yarns. Is this distortion the cause of reduced strength? It seems natural that areas of concentrated distortion would be more likely to serve as nucleation sites for kink band formation. However, as a warning against making sweeping generalizations, work by Adams[7] has shown that idealized geometries which encourage shear can actually lead to easier formation of kink bands and weaker parts.

EFFECT ON COMPRESSION STRENGTH – 2D Glass Triaxial Braid

A series of 15.2x15.2cm (6x6in) flat panels were formed under a range of molding pressures to determine the effect of pressure on distortion and ultimately on panel strength. The panels were formed in a picture frame mold, using a Wabash vacuum hot press. EPON 815 epoxy resin was poured into the bottom of the mold and 6 layers of 2D glass triaxial braid fabric were placed on top. The panels were formed at a range of pressures from 138-3450kPa (20-500psi). Fiber volume fractions (ranging from 0.49-0.71) were calculated from final panel thickness (Table 1) and also by weighing the dry fabric and the formed glass-epoxy panel. The results from both methods were within 2-3% of each other.

Figure 1: Effect of Consolidation Pressure on Glass Triaxial Braid Panel Strength

Table 1: 2D Glass Triaxial Braid Short Block Compression Test

Pressure (kPa)	Thickness (cm)	Fib Vf	Load (kN)	Stiffness (MN/m)	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)
138	0.82	0.49	90.9	126.0	290.9	17.9
345	0.73	0.56	79.6	126.6	284.5	20.1
1380	0.61	0.68	64.9	122.3	280.8	23.5
3450	0.57	0.71	53.7	114.3	247.9	23.4

** values represent averages of 4 test specimens

NASA Short Block (4.4cm x 3.8cm x *t* specimens) compression strength values were determined for each of the panels. As can be seen from Figure 1, the maximum compressive strength decreased significantly with the increase in pressure. In contrast, the modulus increased at the lower pressures and then leveled off after 1380kPa (200psi). Surprisingly enough, Cox's [2] results from lightly and heavily compacted 3D interlock weaves showed opposite results - higher strengths for heavily compacted (1500kPa) specimens. Cox describes the failure of the lightly compacted specimens to be due to kink band formation versus delamination failure for the heavily compacted specimens. The difference in outcome is most likely a result of the substantial z-component in these 3D weaves versus the 2D triaxial braids. In the angle interlock weaves, the warp weavers traversing in the z-direction are inclined at a large angle to the loading axis, providing less resistance to axial compression. As the material is compacted, this angle decreases, resulting in greater axial stiffness and strength. In contrast, in the 2D braids, as will be seen later, high levels of compression can actually lead to a greater off-axis component.

An argument can also be made that the load and stiffness values should be examined independent of thickness (i.e., N and N/m, respectively) because the load is expected to be carried primarily by the fibers, rather than by the changing amount of resin due to pressure. Examination of this data shows that an even greater drop is seen in the load but the modulus trend is inverted (see Table 1). With some pressure (345kPa), the modulus and stiffness both increased, suggesting better alignment. However, there is a rapid drop in stiffness (N/m) at the high pressure but an increase in modulus if thickness is taken into account. This result seems to support the dominant effect of the reinforcement. If the amount of resin is critical, normalizing by the thickness of resin should lead to relatively

Figure 2: Photomicrograph of Carbon Triaxial Braid showing increased distortion at 3450kPa vs. 345kPa consolidation pressure (viewed along 45deg braider angle)

constant modulus values. However, if the load is carried primarily by the fibers, dividing by a smaller thickness will clearly lead to higher modulus values.

While thinner specimens are naturally more subject to buckling failure, the dimensions of the specimens and the test configuration (transverse support at both ends) are designed to inhibit buckling failure. A rough calculation of the critical buckling load for these samples shows that the Euler buckling load is approximately five times higher than the measured failure load. Examination of the failure specimens also did not show any trend towards buckling failure in the thin panels versus the thicker panels.

Photomicrographs of the specimens showed significant distortion in the yarns at the 3450kPa(500psi) pressure, while much less distortion was visible at the 345kPa(50psi) pressure. Because the poor contrast in the glass triaxial braid photos leads to poor reproduction, the figure shown (Figure 2) is for a carbon triaxial braid subjected to the same processing conditions and displaying similar features as were observed for the glass.

Although parts are not typically formed at pressures as high as 3450kPa, there are regions in complex parts where localized pressures may reach high values and fiber geometries may encourage distortion. The results of these experiments suggest that some detrimental deformation or damage is occurring during forming at high pressures.

YARN DEFORMATION – Plain Weave Glass Fabrics

Since the yarn distortion in the triaxial braids seemed to be a primary cause of the strength reduction, further studies were attempted to understand the deformation mechanisms. Because of the relative simplicity of the geometry of the plain weave, several experiments were run using these forms. A similar set of 15.2x15.2cm panels were produced. Two types of plain weave glass fabrics were used, a standard Type 162 – 11x6.3 ends/cm, 0.40 kg/m² (28x16epi, 11.8 oz/yd²) and a very large tow weave. Panels containing 8 layers of Type 162 fabrics were formed at pressures ranging from 138-1380kPa. The discrete points in Figure 3 represent the displacement (Δ thickness) and volume fraction change with applied pressure.

Figure 3: Pressure-Displacement Behavior of Glass Plain Weave (dry fabric and cured panels)

Samples from each panel were cut, polished, and photographed. At pressures below 348kPa, there was very little deformation of the sinusoidal undulation of the yarns. The large changes in thickness seemed to be primarily a result of resin squeeze out. In contrast, observations of panels subjected to higher pressures indicated increasing flattening and shifting of tows with increasing pressure.

In order to gain a better understanding of the actual deformation during consolidation, the large tow glass fabric was placed into a mold with one plexiglass side. As pressure was applied in this dry compaction test, the *in-situ* deformation of the fabric cross-section could be recorded. A preliminary compaction test confirmed a similar pressure vs. displacement curve for 8 layers of dry 162 fabric as was obtained from the panels produced with resin (Figure 3, solid line).

As expected from the previous consolidation panels, the originally sinusoidal yarn began to distort only after most of the space between the layers had been removed and the pressure had begun its steep ascent, indicating significant direct tow-to-tow contact in the z-direction (Figure 4). Attempts were made to quantify this distortion, but automated image analysis tracking of the yarns while they distorted proved to be extremely difficult and inconsistent. Nevertheless, general statements can be made about tow flattening and some in-plane movement of the tows. Rather than remaining in a perfectly in-phase orientation, individual tows in the neighboring layers tended to shift to one side or the other in order to create a higher packing density (Figure 5).

At what pressure does this shift occur? The answer probably depends on several factors, including friction [8] and tow size. As pressure is applied, two primary modes of deformation occur – change in crimp or sinusoidal undulations of the tows and flattening of the tows themselves. These deformation modes exist in series, with the less resistant mode producing the greater displacement. Using an analysis derived by Cai and Gutowski [9] for fiber bundles, the bulk compressive behavior can be represented as

$$P = \frac{3\pi E}{\beta^4} \frac{(1 - \sqrt{\frac{V_j}{V_i}})}{(\sqrt{\frac{V_{max}}{V_j}} - 1)^4} \quad (1)$$

Figure 4: In-situ Distortion of Glass Plain Weave During Compaction

Figure 5: Schematic of Tow Movement

Figure 6: Relative Contribution of Tow Flattening and Tow Undulation Reduction

where β = arch length/height ratio and V_{-} represents the initial, corresponding, and maximum volume fractions.

For pressure related to flattening of the tows, values used are those representing the fiber ($E = 70\text{GPa}$, $\beta = 100$). For pressure related to reduction of the tow undulation, the values used represent the fabric material and structure ($E = 24\text{GPa}$, $\beta = 30$). The results are plotted in Figure 6. Given these parameters, the results qualitatively match observations. Namely, at lower pressures, greater deformation is due to tow flattening, while the undulations remain sinusoidal. As the tows approach a critical volume fraction at higher pressures, further displacement must occur as a result of change in tow undulation or distortion.

CONCLUSION

Results from a series of controlled experiments relating consolidation pressure and material response indicate that even in flat panels, high pressures can cause geometric distortion, leading to significant reduction in strength. Deformation response to pressure takes the form of resin squeeze out, tow flattening, and changes in tow undulation. In some cases, a reduction in undulation can occur, improving strength. However, in the case of high pressures and/or complex geometries, greater distortion and nonuniformity develops, with a negative impact on strength.

The acceptability of distortion depends on its effect on properties such as strength. Variations in fiber architectures are accepted as inherent to textile materials. Critical manufacturing specifications generally include controls on variations such as tow angle deviation – e.g., is $\pm 1^\circ$ necessary or is $\pm 3^\circ$ or $\pm 5^\circ$ sufficient? Tighter specifications mean higher cost. Yet, in many cases, it is not clear what tolerances are acceptable. This is also an important issue in deciding what level of variation must be accounted for in a strength model. An experimental study is currently underway to determine the sensitivity of strength to global variations in braid angle.

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References

- [1] J.E. Masters, R.L. Foye, C.M. Pastore, and Y.A. Gowayed, Mechanical Properties of Triaxially Braided Composites: Experimental and Analytical Results. *J. Comp. Tech. Res.*, ASTM, 112-122 (1993).
- [2] B.N. Cox, W.C. Carter, M.S. Dadkhah, and W.L. Morris, Micromechanics of Fatigue in Woven and Stitched Composites. NASA Contractor Report 4626, September, (1994).
- [3] T.W. Chou and F.K. Ko, eds., *Textile Structural Composites*, Elsevier Science Publ, New York, (1989).
- [4] J.D. Whitcomb. Three-Dimensional Stress Analysis of Plain Weave Composites, in *Composite Materials: Fatigue and Fracture (3rd Vol)*, ASTM STP 1110, ed. T.K. O'Brien, ASTM 417-438, (1991)
- [5] R.A. Naik, Analysis of Woven and Braided Fabric Reinforced Composites. NASA Contractor Report 194930, June, (1994).
- [6] C.M. Pastore, Quantification of processing artifacts in textile composites. *Composites Manufacturing*, 4, n.4, 217-226 (1993).
- [7] D.O. Adams, personal communication, Summer (1994)
- [8] J. Chen and T.M. McBride, Measurement of Unit Cell Deformation in Forming of Textile Composites. *Processing, Design, and Performance of Composite Materials*, ASME WAM, Nov. 6-11, (1994).
- [9] Z. Cai and T. Gutowski, The 3-D Deformation Behavior of a Lubricated Fiber Bundle. *J. Composite Materials*, 26, n.8, 1207-1237 (1992).